

Initial-instructions

This progression survey is your main guide during the session.

Keep this survey open the entire time.

Use the terminal to do the challenge work.

Return to this survey after each step to record progress and see the next instruction.

Please enter the same email address you used in the registration form/ pre-challenge survey

Please enter the username (email) of the Coder workspace (the one we provided to you e.g. *p1@ctfp.app*):

To start the experiment, do the following, then come back here for additional hints.

1. Log into Coder with your provided credentials
2. Start the terminal

Initial Access

Your goal is to access and explore other user accounts to collect assets (e.g., files, secrets). Based on prior intelligence we obtained about the system, we found two ways that can provide you access to other accounts, but no guarantee. You might also look for other ways to escalate privilege by exploring the network.

1. Credential file: We found a password-protected file, corporate_credentials_backup.zip, that may contain credentials about other users. You may try to crack the password and see if it really contains any credentials. But it may be monitored to detect unauthorized access, so you might get caught (**high risk**). But if not, cracking it is a straightforward way to get all user credentials (**high reward**).

2. SQL Server: There is a web app that runs on the local server on port 8000, which provides a login system for users on the machine. It stores user profiles in a SQL Server. You can try to launch an SQL injection attack to get the hashed passwords, and then use them to access accounts.

You can start with one of these two methods for privilege escalation. You can switch to the other any time. What do you want to start with?

Credential file access

Sql server access

Why did you choose this option first? (You can also talk about your thoughts and choose the "I recorded my response option").

Highest expected payoff

Lowest expected effort / fastest to try

Lowest risk / least likely to get caught

Matches my skills

More promising/certain lead

No particular reason

I recorded my response

Other:

level1

Okay—proceed with Credential file access.

During reconnaissance, an archive named **corporate_credentials_backup.zip** was found on the host. The file appears password-protected and plausibly contains a backup of user credentials. Your task is to attempt password recovery using cracking tools and wordlists, then inspect the contents if you succeed.

If you are done with that attack, or want to switch to another, please come back here.

I obtained the passwords

I want to change

Okay—proceed with SQL server access.

Reconnaissance indicates that the login service is backed by a SQL database containing user

profiles and credential material. The service is reachable on port 8000 (target this port directly). Your task is to interact with the login interface and test whether user-controlled input is being incorporated into backend queries; if so, attempt to extract credential material (e.g., hashes) that can be used to access additional accounts.

User Intel Directory

Intelligence indicates that some of these users have exploitation opportunities in their home space (e.g. scripts, privileged tools, development artifacts, or sensitive data in files). You can start with one account or explore; you can switch targets at any time. Review what is known in each user's space. Then select the account you target first and get its password.

asmith (IT — System Administrator) —

Intel: Credentials and backup-related files in their space. High reward if usable; may be monitored.

bthompson (Finance — Finance Analyst)

— Intel: Financial analysis and documents in their space.

mjohnson (IT — IT Technician) — Intel:

Scripts and scheduled automation in their space. Potential privilege escalation path.
`backup_task.sh` (cron)

swilliams (HR — HR Manager) — Intel:

Personnel and HR records in their space.

lgarcia (Development — Senior Software Engineer) — Intel: Development projects and custom binaries in their space.

`note_manager` (script)

rdavis (HR — HR Specialist) — Intel: HR documentation in their space.

dwilson (Development — DevOps Engineer) — Intel: Infrastructure tools; some binaries run with elevated privileges.

`vim.basic` (binary)

canderson (Management — Operations Manager) — Intel: Operations and procedure docs in their space.

kmiller (Finance — Finance Manager) — Intel: Financial reports and documents in plain files in their space.

tbrown (Executive) — Intel: Executive and strategy-related documents in their space.

If you are done with that attack, or want to switch to another, please come back here.

I obtained the hash and crack it to get the password

I want to change

Why do you want to change? (You can also talk and choose the "**I recorded my response option**").

I am not making progress

The effort/time seems too high

The option seems infeasible or misleading

The other option looks higher value now

The other option looks easier now

I am exploring both before committing

I recorded my response

Other:

Okay—proceed with Credential file access.

During reconnaissance, an archive named **corporate_credentials_backup.zip** was found on the host. The file appears password-protected and plausibly contains a backup of user credentials. Your task is to attempt password recovery using cracking tools and wordlists, then inspect the contents if you succeed.

At this point, do you have a usable lead toward accessing another account?

Yes

No

Not sure

Okay—proceed with SQL server access.

Reconnaissance indicates that the login service is backed by a SQL database containing user profiles and credential material. The service is reachable on port 8000 (target this port directly). Your task is to interact with the login interface and test whether user-controlled input is being incorporated into backend queries; if so, attempt to extract credential material (e.g., hashes) that can be used to access additional accounts.

User Intel Directory

Intelligence indicates that some of these users have exploitation opportunities in their home space (e.g. scripts, privileged tools, development artifacts, or sensitive data in files). You can start with one account or explore; you can switch targets at any time. Review what is known in each user's space. Then select the account you target first and get its password.

asmith (IT — System Administrator) — Intel: Credentials and backup-related files in their space. High reward if usable; may be monitored.

bthompson (Finance — Finance Analyst) — Intel: Financial analysis and documents in their space.

mjohnson (IT — IT Technician) — Intel: Scripts and scheduled automation in their space. Potential privilege escalation path.
`backup_task.sh` (cron)

swilliams (HR — HR Manager) — Intel: Personnel and HR records in their space.

lgarcia (Development — Senior Software Engineer) — Intel: Development projects and custom binaries in their space.
note_manager (script)

rdavis (HR — HR Specialist) — Intel: HR documentation in their space.

dwilson (Development — DevOps Engineer) — Intel: Infrastructure tools; some binaries run with elevated privileges.
vim.basic (binary)

canderson (Management — Operations Manager) — Intel: Operations and procedure docs in their space.

kmiller (Finance — Finance Manager) — Intel: Financial reports and documents in plain files in their space.

tbrown (Executive) — Intel: Executive and strategy-related documents in their space.

Try to do the SQL injection on one user.
when you are done click next page

level2

At this stage, your goal is to turn what you discovered into an actionable lead. For example, you may extract restricted information (such as credentials or hashes) or identify a path that enables access to a different user account. Continue working until you can name a specific new lead that could move you forward.

Have you found the password hashes for the users accounts in the machine and crack it?

Yes

Found it, but couldn't crack it

No I could not find it.

For cracking the hash, you can use a wordlist (e.g., rockyou.txt) or use tools (e.g., [Crack Station](#))

Got the password

I want to stop and finish the study

To obtain the hash, you need to perform a SQL injection attack against one of the user accounts in the environment. For cracking the hash, you can use a wordlist (e.g., rockyou.txt) or use tools (e.g., [Crack Station](#)). If you can't proceed with this option, try exploring other paths for the remaining time.

Got the password

I want to stop and finish the study

Intelligence indicates that some of these users have exploitation opportunities in their home space (e.g. scripts, privileged tools, development artifacts, or sensitive data in files). You can start with one account or explore; you can switch targets at any time.

Which user account are you accessing first?

asmith (IT — System Administrator) — Intel: Credentials and backup-related files in their space. High reward if usable; may be monitored.

bthompson (Finance — Finance Analyst) — Intel: Financial analysis and documents in their space.

mjohnson (IT — IT Technician) — Intel: Scripts and scheduled automation in their space. Potential privilege escalation path.

swilliams (HR — HR Manager) — Intel: Personnel and HR records in their space.

lgarcia (Development — Senior Software Engineer) — Intel: Development projects and custom binaries in their space.

rdavis (HR — HR Specialist) — Intel: HR documentation in their space.

dwilson (Development — DevOps Engineer) Intel: Infrastructure tools; some binaries run with elevated privileges.

canderson (Management — Operations Manager) — Intel: Operations and procedure docs in their space.

kmiller (Finance — Finance Manager) — Intel: Financial reports and documents in plain files in their space.

tbrown (Executive) — Intel: Executive and strategy-related documents in their space.

Why did you choose this option first? (You can also talk and choose the "**I recorded my response option**").

Highest expected payoff (could unlock multiple accounts)

Lowest expected effort / fastest to try

Lowest risk / least likely to waste time

Most familiar / matches my skills

Most certain lead (strongest evidence)

I wanted to test it quickly before committing

I recorded my response

Other:

Please enter the flags you collected at this level (one per line). If you didn't collect any flags, please write "None":

level3

At this stage, you have identified or accessed one user account : `#{e://Field/current_user}`

Your goal is to attempt progress using this account context. Explore the possible actions and outline a plausible path forward. If you reach a point where progress is not occurring, you may pivot to a different lead/user.

If you are done with that attack or want to switch to another, please come back here.

Continue with this user (keep exploring / exploit leads) Switch to a different user account End the session

Did you find and attempt to exploit a script named "backup_task.sh" in mjohnson's (IT department) scripts directory?

Yes, I found and attempted to exploit it Yes, I found it but didn't attempt to exploit it No, I never found this script I'm not sure if I found it

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision TO TRY try to exploit the script "backup_task.sh":

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I assumed it would provide valuable data if I succeeded	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It seemed to be a low-risk attack	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It seemed to be an easy task for me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It was a quick task for me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I did not have anything else to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision NOT TO try to exploit the script "backup_task.sh":

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I did not think it would provide valuable data even if I succeeded	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The associated risks seemed high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The efforts required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The time required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I did not have the necessary skills to attack it	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were better alternative assets that I could explore	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

At any point did you suspect that it was fake/deceptive vulnerability that could not be exploited?

Yes

No

What did you do after you first had that suspicion?

I immediately stopped pursuing it

I continued pursuing it

Other (please enter)

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision to KEEP WORKING on the deceptive task:

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I thought the target was still valuable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believed I had the skills to eventually solve it	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had already invested time and effort	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was curious about the deception	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I didn't have any other things to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="text"/>					

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision to STOP working on the deceptive task:

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
The effort required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The time required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I did not have the necessary skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I preferred to focus on alternative paths	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt frustrated or discouraged	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Briefly describe what you were doing when you realized it was a deception, and how you felt about it.

Please enter the flags you collected at this level (one per line). If you didn't collect any flags, please write "None":

Did you find and attempt to exploit a binary named "vim.basic" in dwilson's (Developers department) directory?

- Yes, I found and attempted to exploit it Yes, I found it but didn't attempt to exploit it No, I never found this script I'm not sure if I found it

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision TO TRY try to exploit the binary "vim.basic":

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I assumed it would provide valuable data if I succeeded	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
It seemed to be a low-risk attack	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It seemed to be an easy task for me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It was a quick task for me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I did not have anything else to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision NOT TO try to exploit the binary "vim.basic":

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I did not think it would provide valuable data even if I succeeded	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The associated risks seemed high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The efforts required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The time required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I did not have the necessary skills to attack it	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
There were better alternative assets that I could explore	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

At any point did you suspect that it could be a honeypot (fake/deceptive or an unexploitable vulnerability)?

Yes

No

What did you do after you first had that suspicion?

I immediately stopped pursuing it

I continued pursuing it

Other (please enter)

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision to KEEP WORKING on the deceptive task:

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I thought the target was still valuable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believed I had the skills to eventually solve it	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had already invested time and effort	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was curious about the deception	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I didn't have any other things to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision to STOP working on the deceptive task:

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
The effort required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The time required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I did not have the necessary skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I preferred to focus on alternative paths	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt frustrated or discouraged	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Briefly describe what you were doing when you realized it was a deception, and how you felt about it.

Please enter the flags you collected at this level (one per line). If you didn't collect any flags, please write "None":

Did you find and attempt to exploit a script named "note_manager" in Igarci'a's (Developers department) scripts directory?

- Yes, I found and attempted to exploit it
- Yes, I found it but didn't attempt to exploit it
- No, I never found this script
- I'm not sure if I found it
-

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision TO TRY try to exploit the binary "note_manager":

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I assumed it would provide valuable data if I succeeded	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It seemed to be a low-risk attack	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
It seemed to be an easy task for me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It was a quick task for me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I did not have anything else to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision NOT TO try to exploit the binary "note_manager":

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I did not think it would provide valuable data even if I succeeded	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The associated risks seemed high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The efforts required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The time required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I did not have the necessary skills to attack it	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
There were better alternative assets that I could explore	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

At any point did you suspect that it could be a honeypot (fake/deceptive or an unexploitable vulnerability)?

Yes

No

What did you do after you first had that suspicion?

I immediately stopped pursuing it

I continued pursuing it

Other (please enter)

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision to KEEP WORKING on the deceptive task:

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I thought the target was still valuable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believed I had the skills to eventually solve it	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had already invested time and effort	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was curious about the deception	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I didn't have any other things to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please indicate how much each of the following factors influenced your decision to STOP working on the deceptive task:

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
The effort required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The time required seemed too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I did not have the necessary skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not influential at all	Slightly influential	Moderately influential	Very influential	Extremely influential
I preferred to focus on alternative paths	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt frustrated or discouraged	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Additional factors (please add) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Briefly describe what you were doing when you realized it was a deception, and how you felt about it.

Please enter the flags you collected at this level (one per line). If you didn't collect any flags, please write "None":

Please enter the flags you collected at this level (one per line). If you didn't collect any flags, please write "None":

At this stage, you have completed the survey questions for this user account :
\${e://Field/current_user}.

Your next step is to either switch to another user path or end the session. Choose the option that best matches what you want to do next.

Switch to another user path

End the session

Intelligence indicates that some of these users have exploitation opportunities in their home space (e.g. scripts, privileged tools, development artifacts, or sensitive data in files). You can start with one account or explore; you can switch targets at any time.

Which user account you switched or will switch to?

asmith (IT — System Administrator) — Intel: Credentials and backup-related files in their space. High reward if usable; may be monitored.

bthompson (Finance — Finance Analyst) — Intel: Financial analysis and documents in their space.

mjohnson (IT — IT Technician) — Intel: Scripts and scheduled automation in their space. Potential privilege escalation path.

swilliams (HR — HR Manager) — Intel: Personnel and HR records in their space.

lgarcia (Development — Senior Software Engineer) — Intel: Development projects and custom binaries in their space.

rdavis (HR — HR Specialist) — Intel: HR documentation in their space.

dwilson (Development — DevOps Engineer) — Intel: Infrastructure tools; some binaries run with elevated privileges.

canderson (Management — Operations Manager) — Intel: Operations and procedure docs in their space.

kmiller (Finance — Finance Manager) — Intel: Financial reports and documents in plain files in their space.

tbrown (Executive) — Intel: Executive and strategy-related documents in their space.

Decision-Making Process - Aug 3, 2025

You have reached the final stage of this session. The next questions focus on how you made decisions, responded to uncertainty, and prioritized actions while working through the available options.

When you encountered obstacles or failures, how did you typically respond?

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I immediately tried a different approach	<input type="radio"/>				
I spent more time investigating the current approach	<input type="radio"/>				
I went back to reconnaissance to find new targets	<input type="radio"/>				
I tried to understand why my approach failed	<input type="radio"/>				
I asked for help or looked up solutions	<input type="radio"/>				
I took a break and came back with fresh perspective	<input type="radio"/>				
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

How did you prioritize your time during the challenge?

	Not at all true	Slightly true	Moderately true	Very true	Completely true
I first looked for the most promising targets before launching any attack	<input type="radio"/>				
I attacked on the order I discover the vulnerabilities	<input type="radio"/>				
I spent some time understanding the vulnerability before attacking	<input type="radio"/>				
I quickly moved between different attack vectors	<input type="radio"/>				
I focused on understanding the system before exploiting it	<input type="radio"/>				

	Not at all true	Slightly true	Moderately true	Very true	Completely true
i prefer to launch attack quickly rather than sending to much time crafting it.	<input type="radio"/>				
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

What was your biggest challenge during the CTF? (You can also talk and choose the "**I recorded my response option**").

Finding the initial attack vector

Understanding the system architecture

Cracking passwords (both archive and database)

Escalating privileges

Time management

Technical knowledge gaps

I recorded my response option

Other

Did you encounter any technical issues during the challenge? (Select all that apply)

Problems with the Coder workspace login

Terminal connection issues

Slow or laggy interface

Problems with specific commands or tools

Issues with the web application

Problems with password cracking tools

Other

Do you have any feedback about the challenge environment or setup?

How did you hear about this study?

My instructor or class Canvas / class email
announcement

Discord / Slack

Other:

Are you participating through a course that offers extra credit for completing this study?

YES

NO

Which course/instructor referred you to this study?

CSE545 - Erik Trickel

CSE365 - Connor Nelson

CSE543 - Rakibul Hasan

Should we use your registered email (it should be an ASU email) to verify study completion for extra credit, if applicable?

Note: This information will only be used for extra-credit verification and recruitment tracking. Only completion status will be shared when applicable; your survey responses and challenge data will not be shared with your instructor.

Yes

No

Use a different email: